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POSSIBILITIES OF USING EFFECTIVE MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

Abstract: *The article analyzes methods such as vitagen, reflexive, and facilitative technologies, as well as techniques like boomerang, finding connections, SWOT analysis, and ethical dilemmas, which have been identified as effective in teaching philosophical sciences within the education system. The potential of these methods to serve socially oriented tasks in preparing future professionals is outlined. The article introduces teachers and students of philosophical sciences to methods that facilitate a comprehensive understanding of philosophical issues.*

Keywords: *method, pedagogical technology, social function, philosophical education, modern pedagogical approaches.*

The Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 has outlined 100 goals across 7 priority directions to comprehensively advance the country, ensure the prosperous life of its people, and continue reforms aimed at forming active civil society institutions. Specifically, Goal 70, titled “Improving State Policy on Youth,” focuses on promoting the spiritual, intellectual, physical, and moral development of youth, ensuring open and high-quality education, and providing comprehensive educational opportunities at all levels. Achieving these objectives requires organizing the teaching of philosophical sciences in education using innovative pedagogical technologies and interactive methods.

The use of pedagogical technologies and methods that enhance the effectiveness of philosophical science classes in educational institutions contributes to the realization of the aforementioned goals. Below, we analyze the effectiveness potential of the following technologies and methods:

Vitagen Technologies – These are technologies used in selecting educational content, aimed at solving real-life problems and transforming knowledge into competencies through the unity of theory and practice. “The essence of vitagen technologies lies in the concepts of life experience and skills”¹⁶⁸. These concepts can be observed in the transformation of a student’s personality—information frequently encountered, identified, and widely applied in life experience—into life experience, or vitagen experience. This technology teaches students to think

¹⁶⁸ Нарзикулова Д.Х. Таълимни ахборотлаштириш шароитида педагогик низоларнинг профилактик технологияларини такомиллаштириш, Пед. фан. бўйича (PhD)...дисс. автореф. – Самарқанд –2018.: -16- б.

scientifically while performing tasks related to a specific topic, work collaboratively in groups, and critically analyze the subject or phenomenon being studied. Specifically, vitagen technologies enable students to apply theoretical and practical knowledge in real-life processes through methods such as controversial lectures, brainstorming, case studies, and boomerang techniques. The use of case studies in philosophical science classes fosters the development of several important qualities in students, including:

- Teaching objective thinking;
- Facilitating harmony between theory and practice;
- Creating multiple alternative approaches to problem-solving;
- Enhancing the ability to accept others' opinions;
- Cultivating a sense of responsibility.

“Facilitative Technologies – These guide students to complete educational tasks in small groups during the learning process, leading to the formation of a facilitator-leader. Preparing facilitators with experience in creative activities for the theoretical analysis of social-ethical issues is of great importance”¹⁶⁹.

The use of the “Boomerang” method in philosophical education creates opportunities for applying modern pedagogical approaches. This method enhances students' social activity. One of its main advantages is that it fosters independent thinking and assimilation skills, contributing to the formation of a healthy worldview. For instance, assigning articles such as “What is the benefit of philosophy?”, “Why are social-humanitarian sciences necessary?”, or “Why is it important to study history?” and then applying the knowledge gained through this method allows students to gain a comprehensive understanding of the social significance of philosophical sciences.

Reflective Technologies – These are technologies that enable students to reinforce and develop their acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies by applying them in new and unexpected situations. Reflective technologies require a system that allows students to perform mental operations while completing educational tasks. Students are divided into groups: the first group proposes a project addressing a problematic situation, the second group suggests ways to optimize it, and the third group analyzes it, proposing the most effective solution for the discussion. As a component of reflective discussion, a reflective polylogue is embodied. The purpose of the reflective polylogue is to independently analyze problems by activating and developing creative potential.

Phenomenological Method – This method is based on perceiving reality through human consciousness and experience, taking into account subjective experience and its complexity. For example, when studying contemporary ethical issues in the subject of Ethics and Aesthetics, examining the opinions and conclusions of several students who have directly witnessed such issues in the classroom enhances the understanding and impact of the topic.

¹⁶⁹ Рахимов.А.К., - Талабаларда табиий-илмий дунёқарашни ривожлантириш методикасини такомиллаштириш (эволюцион таълимот фанини ўқитиш мисолида), Пед.фан.доктори (ДSc)...дисс. автореф. – Т.: 2019. –22 б.

Table 1. Examples of Using the Phenomenological Method

Aesthetic and ethical issues	Relatively supportive opinions	Completely opposing views	Examples of justifying
Tattoo			
Euthanasia			
Death			

This method helps to understand reality deeply through vivid examples, fosters the creation of new concepts and ideas, and proves the importance of subjective experience.

Ethical Dilemmas Method. The use of the ethical dilemmas method, not only in Ethics and Aesthetics but also in all philosophical science classes and independent learning sessions, promotes the development of students' critical thinking, argumentation, and ethical decision-making skills.

Table 2. Content Related to the Use of the Ethical Dilemmas Method.

Situation	I support this action	I am against cases of law violation	Aspects of using an integrative approach and reflective technologies
	Causes and		
The doctor handed Citizen A a list of prescribed medications for their child and stated that, despite it being 2:00 AM, the medicine must be brought within 20 minutes. The representative of the nearest pharmacy (Pharmacy 1) informed Citizen A that the required medicine was not available but was definitely available at the adjacent pharmacy, which only operates during the day. Citizen A broke into Pharmacy 2, took the necessary medicine, and left a note with their phone number and a promise to compensate for all damages caused. At 4:00 AM, the doctor noted that the patient's condition had improved, emphasizing the critical importance of the medicine being delivered on time.	-	-	What approach do practitioners consider appropriate in such a situation? What is the essence and content of the principle of expediency? Can this situation be cited as an example of "extreme necessity" among the circumstances excluding the criminality of an act in the Criminal Law and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights?

Hermeneutic Method. This method aids students in achieving deep understanding, critical analysis, cultural awareness, self-understanding, and the

development of dialogue by interpreting various source texts and socio-cultural phenomena. It is effective in explaining human philosophy, ethical principles, and uncovering the essence behind wise sayings. For example, J. Rumi’s statement, “Let us learn to read ourselves before reading books,” may seem difficult to grasp at first glance. However, by analyzing the author’s intent, a deeper approach reveals its true meaning.

Finding Connections Method. This method enables students to gain a general understanding of the significance of the constituent elements of the studied object within the system of social issues and their connections with other spheres of society. For instance, in the subject of social philosophy, when explaining the topic “Main Spheres of Social Life and Factors of Development,” emphasizing the importance of each social institution helps reinforce students’ knowledge of dialectical laws. The “finding connections” method also serves to achieve the objectives of the subject in the topic “Globalistics – the Philosophy of Global Problems.”

Table 3. Philosophical Analysis of the Interconnectedness of Global Problems.

Global problem.	Contributing factors.	Ways to eliminate	UN statistical facts
Famine.	Illiteracy, wars, corruption...	Providing employment to the population, teaching vocational skills, achieving efficiency in the education system.	Every 7 minutes, a child dies of hunger worldwide. To eradicate famine, \$80 billion—0.5% of global income—is needed.
Illiteracy.	Demographic explosion, famine, poverty.	Restricting child labor.	
Peace issue.	Arms trade, drug trafficking, illiteracy, extremism and terrorism, drug	Strengthening knowledge and enlightenment, developing international	UN statistical facts.

Considering the characteristics of the audience and the worldviews of students when using each method contributes to effectiveness.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of methods based on modern pedagogical approaches in the educational process not only fosters an active civic stance among youth but also prepares them to address pressing issues in their future professional activities.

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